

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101059548.

**OPEN EARTH
MONITOR**

MS5: Open-Earth-Monitor EU and global case studies 1st release

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Document control page

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Executive Summary

The Earth Monitor Web-App and data sets primarily aim at serving third parties from the thirty two use-cases, which are also aligned with the EU programmes / objectives. Several tools have been implemented and released, most importantly the Tier 1 data geoportal has been published (<https://app.EarthMonitor.org>) — this will be the central landing page for all most significant layers and requires less specialized knowledge (i.e. a service of one-click operation to watch a geostory; follow link to find out more about the data & science behind). The Open-Earth-Monitor App will remain the central access point (for simplicity) where all targeted communities / use cases can quickly find and visualize project products produced by all partners in the consortium (1-mouse-click to get engaged). We find it important that the app is simple to use, self-explanatory and requires no professional training. This way we can maximize the impact and potentially reach all EU citizens. In addition to the Tier-1 App, a second version of the Tier 2 data portal <https://OpenLandMap.org> has been published and several releases of the OpenEO software including the [sits pkg](#) integration. A video recording of the public launch of the Open-Earth-Monitor App which explains all targeted functionality is also available [via our Youtube channel](#).

App.EarthMonitor.org: listing and exploring monitors from hub tab

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Introduction

Part of the objectives of WP5 and WP6 involve developing a data and analysis portal for earth observation and monitoring. Whilst WP5 serves EU governance and support EU programmes with special focus on European Green Deal actions, WP6 monitor the state of the planet and to support global programmes (eg. GEOSS and UNFCCC). To achieve this, a suite of tools will be developed to directly serve EU citizens, i.e. easy-to-use data portals and desktop and mobile phone app. The Earth Monitor Web App was released and launched on 19th December 2023. Three more major updates of the App.EarthMonitor.org are planned:

- During the [Open-Earth-Monitor Global Workshop 2024](#) (first week October 2024): the app should be then 85% completed and functional;
- In 2025 during the the Open-Earth-Monitor Global workshop 2025: the app should be 95% completed and functional;
- Final closing meeting of the project in 2026 can final update of the app, now fully functionality and serving all datasets in Tier-1;

The global datasets can contribute towards making data-driven diagnostics of the state of the Earth. Furthermore, the different tools and datasets help monitor the state of the Earth with respect to climate change mitigation and adaptation goals. All the tasks from which the monitors have been derived under WP5&6 produced at least one case study for each developed tool. Tasks "T5.01 Development of a generic front-end visualization framework" (led by Vizzuality) is laden with the responsibility to produce a solution (geoportal) for the OEMC project to allow groups to independently build visualizations / geostories and to ensure maximum outreach (fast, complete / self-explanatory, native design, responsive etc).

The Earth Monitor Web-App

The Earth Monitor Web-app is the central publishing platform where all OEMC monitors. The final products from parties that will be published on the Earth Monitor Web-App went through minimum metadata and quality control such as registration of the data, scientific publication, code and processes via the official project sites (zenodo, earthmonitor.org and github). Some functionalities on the app include: i) geostories starting as a specific location and zoom level on the app; ii) users can explore monitors and their corresponding data sets independently from geostories; and ii) users can configure layer opacity when comparison feature is activated.

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Fig. 1: The current design of the OEMC App clearly links Monitors, geo-stories, publications and data sets. We aim at seamless integration of data, discoveries and tools for the general public.

Figure 2: Landing page of the <https://app.earthmonitor.org/>

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Figure 3: Overview of the monitors from the app.earthmonito.org.

Figure 4: Appearance of a monitor on its URL. There are options to visit the datasets, geostories, hub, data catalog (linked to zenodo) and project site (linked to the earthmonito.org website) from every monitor page.

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Monitors and Geostories

The Open Earth Monitor Cyber Infrastructure identified twenty-three different monitors to observe changes within the Earth. These monitors are composed of one or more geostories which talk about some of the most impactful data from the WP4, WP5 and WP6 that directly serves/links the use-cases and related publications. Every geostory has an underlying layer of maps from various EO data which it tracks. These layers appear as monthly or yearly observation series. Additionally, these datasets are viewed as datasets in the app in a manner which is easily understandable by the general public.

To categorize these monitors and geostories, six different themes were chosen. These categories serve as hashtags for ease of findability for users. The categories are:

1. Agriculture
2. Forest
3. Soil
4. Biodiversity
5. Climate and health
6. Water

This list might be revisited. We are also looking at using some existing data vocabularies or similar as used by e.g. EIONET (<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/landcover/>) or similar.

List of Monitors

The table below shows the monitor and its ensuing coverage, theme, associating geostories and links to the Earth Monitor App (<https://app.EarthMonitor.org>).

id	Title (linked to the app.earthmonitor.org)	Coverage	Description	Theme	Use cases
m1	World land degradation neutrality monitor	global	World-land degradation neutrality monitor aims at serving open EO-derived bio-physical indices that can be used to support UNCCD's goal of land degradation neutrality (LDN).	Agriculture	Land Degradation Neutrality tool to support LDN initiative
m2	World reforestation monitor	global	World-reforestation monitor is tracking forest change (gain and loss) ideally near-real time with at least stable annual products available openly.	Forest	World-reforestation monitor use case community conservation Campeche, Mexico

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m3	EU-soil monitor	european	The EU-soil monitor aims at supporting the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO), a system of dashboards to warn organizations about potential negative trends connected to soil degradation.	Soil	EO data and automated mapping for EU soil observatory
m4	EU reforestation planner tool	european	The EU reforestation monitor is developing a digital infrastructure to support planting 3 billion trees (2022-2030) over Europe.	Forest	1. EU reforestation tools based on open EO data 2. Forest management & tracking tools for Croatia
m5	EU forest management tool	european	EU forest management tool is developing AI-based tools to use Copernicus data for rapid forest harvest, disturbance and health monitoring to support the New EU Forest Strategy for 2030.	Forest	EU constructions tracking system in forests
m6	EU coastal monitor	european	The EU coastal monitor will develop virtual research environments for coastal marine monitoring of sea quality, sea pollution and biodiversity.	Biodiversity	Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales
m7	EU biodiversity monitor	european	The EU biodiversity monitor will produce annual estimates of biodiversity at high spatial resolution and make use of spectral characteristics of satellite images to describe landscape or ecosystem heterogeneity as approximations for biodiversity.	Biodiversity	Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tools for IDH
m8	EU crop monitor	european	The EU crop monitor involves monitoring of agriculture activities, state of the crops, climate impact, yield prediction.	Agriculture	1. Crop yield monitoring tools for Africa 2. Tools for Digitalisation of Agriculture in Ethiopia
m9	EU climate monitor	european	The EU climate monitor will investigate impact assessment and financial analysis at high spatial resolution to support EU climate adaptation Strategy and also analyse the vulnerability to climate extremes.	Climate & Health	Meteo support tool for wildfire risk
m10	EU flood monitor	european	This monitor will develop an extreme weather risk monitor tool to support flood prevention in Europe and build upon SM2RAIN precipitation products and Copernicus data for flood mapping.	Water	EU Flood risk maps at high resolution
m11	EU air quality monitor	european	The OEMC Air Quality Monitor provides tools to retrieve, pre-process and interpolate measurement data and covariates at different temporal and spatial resolutions. The displayed maps are prototypes and will be updated later in the project. Similar products for PM2.5, NO2, and O3 will be added.	Climate & Health	1. Air quality assessment at continental scale 2. Air quality assessment at regional scale

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m12	EU snow monitor	europaen	The EU-snow monitor improves the measurement of the Snow Water Equivalent as an estimation of the available water stored in snow covered areas in the Alps. This supports the planning activities of the Hydrological Offices and Hydro Power Generators across the Alps.	Water	High resolution Snow Water Equivalent in selected alpine mountain regions for the Hydrological Office of the Province of Bolzano
m13	EU drought monitor	europaen	The EU drought monitor aims at developing a monitoring tool to support drought and fire hazards prevention in Europe while building upon Copernicus data of vegetation and soil moisture;	Water	Drought Monitoring at high resolution throughout Italy
m14	EU rapid forest disturbance monitor	europaen	This monitor aims at developing a forest disturbances monitoring tool for the EU using 2/3-day coverage of Copernicus Sentinel data to support EU forest management and climate laws.	Forest	EU-rapid forest disturbance monitoring tool
m15	EU land-based mitigation potential impact tool	europaen	This monitor will produce a tool to assess local climatic impacts of land-based mitigation strategies involving land cover changes, such as tree planting or ecosystem restoration, by estimating the potential change in local surface temperatures based on a combination of satellite remote sensing datasets.	Forest	Tool to estimate local temperatures changes following an increase in forest cover
m16	World Drought Monitor	global	The world drought monitor will develop a monitoring tool to support drought and fire hazards at global scale and will build upon existing Copernicus vegetation and soil moisture products.	Water	Global drought monitoring at high resolution
m17	Tropical deforestation monitor	pan-tropics	This monitor aims at the demonstration of an automated, open-source, operational forest disturbance tool across Asia, Africa and South America (also by using the Planet.com 5-m resolution time-series EO data funded by NIFCI) whilst ensuring that the data and information meets the requirements of UNFCCC and REDD.	Forest	1. Soil carbon accounting system for world mangroves 2. Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool
m18	Tropical crop monitor	pan-tropics	The tropical crop monitor serves at the demonstration of an automated, open-source, operational agricultural monitoring tool that meets the requirements of GEOGLAM for tropical countries;	Agriculture	1. Tools for Digitalisation of Agriculture in Ethiopia 2. Crop yield monitoring tools for Africa
m19	Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset	global	This monitor aims at generation of high resolution daily meteorological maps (1 km resolution) for various meteorological variables (temperature, precipitation and sea-level pressure) based on ML-assisted spatio-temporal interpolation of freely available station data.	Climate & Health	1. Meteo-based agricultural insurance tool 2. Data cube for spatial modeling for Sinai

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m20	World flood risk monitor	global	This monitor aims at global hydrology/river-flow predictions to support DestinE and GEOSS / GRAF programmes. It will be built on top of existing data-streams / data-sources (GEOGloWS, HydroSHEDs) but will provide enhanced functionality and easy access including through flexible APIs;	Water	Global topographic and hydrological services based on open topographic data
m21	World forest carbon emissions monitor	global	This monitor aims at development of a global forest GHG emissions monitor combining rapid EO/Copernicus data streams for forest changes and biomass information with a particular focus on natural forests and assessment of commodity supply chains (target products: oil palm, tropical timber, soy, beef, cacao).	Climate & Health	1. Large-area estimation of forest carbon emissions 2. Tools and data for improved biomass estimation
m22	Planet Health Index	global	This monitor serves to develop a framework to resume the complexity and high dimensionality of Earth System data into a set of most relevant and meaningful components by applying statistical techniques, whilst maximizing their physical interpretability. The resulting key metrics would serve to summarise syndromes of change for any point of the world based on 3 axes representing the atmosphere (e.g. drying, warming), the biosphere (e.g. browning, fires) and societal trends (e.g. macroeconomic, land-use).	Climate & Health	Designing a prototype for a planetary health index that could assess systemic risks
m23	World carbon flux monitor	global	The world carbon flux monitor is developing a generic approach for downscaling carbon related variables that are currently too coarse in spatial resolution using ancillary data and hybrid modelling.	Climate & Health	SIF-based high spatial resolution GPP flux estimations

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List of Geostories

id	Title	Connected monitors	Description	Theme	Geostory layer
g1	Urbanization trends (global)	World-land degradation neutrality monitor	Cities are growing rapidly with over 56% of the world's population (4.4 billion) now living in cities. Find out how fast have cities grown from 2000 to 2022 based on the visible night light images at 500 m resolution.	Biodiversity	Night-light images difference (2000-2022)
g2	Losses and gains in primary productivity (global)	World-reforestation monitor World-land degradation neutrality monitor	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR) is one of the key biophysical variables describing primary productivity of world ecosystems. Observe how much has FAPAR changed over the last 20+ years and where are the potential land degradation spots.	Biodiversity	FAPAR based monthly trends (average)
g3	Future vegetation for 2040, 2060 and 2080 (global)	EU-reforestation planner tool World-land degradation neutrality monitor	As we rapidly change our climate we can expect that world vegetation will dynamically follow the new norms. We have tried to predict future distribution of world biomes under different climate change scenarios and provide a glimpse of how the world would look like in the worst case scenario (i.e. RCP 8.5)	Climate & Health	Predicted global biomes (climate change)
g4	Soil bare-fraction dynamics (Europe)	EU-soil monitor EU-crop monitor	Efficient way to track the status of our soils is to quantify and monitor a fraction of bare-earth. For this we used the bimonthly Landsat time-series 2000-2022. Look at the hotspots of potential soil degradation at relatively high spatial resolution (30 m).	Soil	Soil bare-fraction dynamics (2000-2022)
g5	Drought at high resolution in Europe (Europe)	EU-drought monitor World-Drought Monitor	Increasing droughts require distributed data to characterize impacts in a systematic way. Soil moisture content anomalies are a key variable for it but only satellite data can provide enough resolution and coverage to monitor the migrating expansion or lessening of drought conditions across the continent.	Water	Soil moisture index 12,5km resolution HSAF ASCAT h121 over Europe
g7	Soil tillage intensity (Europe)	EU-soil monitor EU-crop monitor	Tillage intensity directly influences soil health and plays a crucial role in the broader context of land degradation. By disturbing the soil, intensive tillage practices can diminish soil structure, reduce organic matter, and increase erosion risk, leading to diminished agricultural productivity and environmental health. Annual tillage intensity maps, created from Normalized Difference Tillage Index (NDTI), provide a vital tool for the monitoring of tillage intensity. Understanding these dynamics allows for the implementation of strategies that can prevent land degradation, ensuring food security and ecosystem resilience for future generations.	Soil	Tillage Intensity (2000-2022)

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g8	Potential reforested map of Europe	EU-reforestation planner tool	<p>Highlight areas where there are ideal conditions for a set of 6 forest tree species (silver fir, beech, spruce, black pine, Scots pine and oak) to be planted but are currently not occupied by said species due to several factors (dispersal issues, competition, co-occurrence of other land-uses). Distribution of individual species can be checked using the species-specific layers. Areas that are already considered urban or agricultural lands are excluded from the analysis regardless of their potential (i.e. our map excludes changes in land uses from agriculture to forest or similar).</p> <p>This map doesn't include climate change scenarios and considers environmental factors to be stable/at equilibrium (for period 2000-2020) so it shouldn't be used for planning tree planting operations for the future; rather it suggests gaps where trees could thrive in current conditions.</p>	Forest	Black pine suitability distribution for planting
g9	Tropical croplands dynamics	Tropical-crop monitor	<p>An important aim of policies aimed at addressing climate change and preserving biodiversity is to eliminate deforestation in the worldwide production chain of vital commodities like palm oil and soybeans. Yet, the scale and changes in deforestation fueled by the expansion of these commodities are not well understood. In this study, we charted the yearly growth of soybean cultivation in South America from 2000 to 2019 using a blend of satellite data and on-site samples. Over this period, the soybean cultivation area more than doubled, increasing from 26.4 million hectares to 55.1 million hectares.</p>	Agriculture	GLAD soybean mapping (2001-2021)
g10	Grasslands and pastureland	World-land degradation neutrality monitor Tropical-crop monitor	<p>Pastures and grasslands are among the most extensive covering approximately 40% of the Earth's surface. Check out the time series of natural grasses and herbaceous cropland over South America.</p>	Agriculture	ESA CCI annual natural grasses
g11	Gross primary productivity	World-land degradation neutrality monitor	<p>This map indicates the general rate of growth or increase in dry plant matter of the ecosystem. However, it's measured in units tailored for agricultural statistics (kg/ha/day). Observations are provided every 10 days, nearly in real-time, on a global scale, with a spatial resolution of 300 meters. These observations cover the time period from 2014 to 2022</p>	Agriculture	Copernicus Gross Dry Matter Productivity (GDMP)
g12	Flood risk index	World-flood risk monitor World-land degradation neutrality monitor	<p>Coastal flooding stands out as one of the most destructive perils faced by coastal regions, with its impact poised to escalate due to Sea Level Rise (SLR), climate variations, and population expansion. Effective mitigation of coastal flooding is imperative, particularly for vulnerable communities in developing nations and small island states. This map delineates historical disasters and alterations in flood-prone regions. Utilizing three Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) – namely MERIT, NASADEM, and LiDAR DTM – in tandem with three spatial resolutions (90m, 1km, and 5km), global coastal flood maps are simulated. These simulations are based on extreme water levels along coastlines with specified return periods, derived from the Deltares dataset, which encapsulates alterations in extreme sea levels under forthcoming climate change scenarios.</p>	Climate & Health	Deltares flood mapping - Returning period 250 (2018 & 2050)

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g13	High-resolution water resources management	EU-drought monitor World-Drought Monitor	Current continental drought monitoring from satellite data struggle to characterize the mosaic of small-scale patterns of drought. This challenges providing effective drought warnings to many end-users. Only recently, satellite missions provided enough resolution of soil moisture to depict the small-scale patterns of drought of interest for agriculture and other sectors. Even in the complex geography of Italy, 1km data from Sentinel-1 accurately uncovers the small-scale patterns of drought compared to previous datasets such as H-SAF ASCAT.	Water	Soil moisture index 1km resolution Sentinel 1-RT1 over Italy
g14	Flood Susceptibility Map Over Mediterranean area	EU-flood monitor World-flood risk monitor	Insurance and re-insurance companies rely on high-resolution Flood Susceptibility Maps (FSMs) for accurate risk assessment. FSMs with 1 km resolution, generated by applying machine learning techniques to multiple satellite images, provide the detailed insights needed to identify areas with high flood probability.	Water	Deltares flood mapping - Returning period 250 (2018 & 2050)
g15	Forest disturbances (Europe)	EU-rapid forest disturbance monitor World-forest carbon emissions monitor	<p>A controversial public and political debate is ongoing on logging activities in Natura 2000 forest sites in Estonia.</p> <p>According to an investigation by the Guardian in 2021, 80% of the forest cover loss in Natura 2000 areas between 2001 and 2019 occurred in the final five years, driven by European demand for biofuels¹. These areas are largely under national protection, but “limited management” is allowed in many forest stands and parks, provided these measures do not harm habitats^{2,3}.</p> <p>Multiple court cases have been launched to force the Estonian Environmental Board to halt issuances of logging permits in protected areas after an infringement filed by the European Commission in 2021⁴. As a result, the Environmental Board temporarily suspended the issuance of logging permits in rare forest habitats within Natura 2000 areas (11% of forested area in Natura sites) in February 2022 for 28 months⁵. However, the adequacy of these measures in meeting the nationally and internationally legally binding requirements for the protection of these habitats continues to be challenged by the European Commission and NGO's alike, as harvesting in surrounding areas is ongoing and deemed harmful to protected habitats.</p> <p>More recently, a petition was initiated by Estonian NGO's calling for the prohibition of clearcutting in nationally protected areas (national parks, nature reserves, landscape protection zones) as well as internationally designated protected areas (Natura 2000)⁶.</p> <p>We used open source high-resolution Sentinel-1 satellite data to develop a wall-to-wall map of forest disturbances in the four-year period between the start of 2020 and end of 2023 in Estonia. We found that logging activities in several Natura 2000 sites under limited management regimes persisted, also after increased restrictions starting in 2022. However, in many protected areas harvesting activities ceased or were non-existent altogether between 2020-2023. We provide one example of each, demonstrating both ongoing and ceased harvesting in protected Estonian forests.</p>	Forest	Disturbance alerts

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			<p>Example Locations:</p> <p>1. Ongoing harvesting activities in Haanja Nature Park Haanja Nature Park is a Natura 2000 site, and largely falls under the national limited management zone regulations. After 2015, clearcutting of up to one hectare was allowed in these zones in order to preserve species and age diversity⁷. Our analysis show that harvesting activities were widespread throughout the area in the period of 2020-2023.</p> <p>2. No harvesting in Laheema special area of conservation after 2021 Restrictions on logging were relaxed in the limited management zones of the Laheema special area of conservation in 2015. According to a NGO report published in March 2021, this resulted in increased harvesting pressures in subsequent years⁸. In our analysis, no harvest activities were detected after 2021, likely as a result of the logging permit issuance ban of 2022. However, harvesting in non-protected forests in the surrounding areas continued throughout the monitoring period.</p>		
g16	Land-use following tropical deforestation	<p>Tropical-deforestation monitor</p> <p>World-forest carbon emissions monitor</p>	<p>Annual land use following deforestation including the EU DR commodities are mapped using sentinel-2 images and Hansen forest loss at 10m resolution. The product initially covers Ethiopia. Of importance, the map highlight expansion of coffee plantations in deforested and degraded forest in Ethiopia critical for supporting EUDR activities. Likewise this data also showcases the expansion of tea plantation in forested areas in Ethiopia. However, small-scale cropland is the dominant cause of deforestation in Ethiopia.</p>	Forest	Land use following deforestation in Ethiopia (2001-2015)
g17	Forest carbon stock and emissions	<p>World-forest carbon emissions monitor</p> <p>Tropical-deforestation monitor</p>	<p>We intend to present a Geostory in two phases: 1) on global forest biomass mapping and 2) on combining them with forest/land use change data to estimate emission</p>	Forest	
g18	Vegetation trait diversity	<p>EU-biodiversity monitor</p> <p>World-reforestation monitor</p>	<p><i>"Disclaimer: The displayed maps are not yet the final products. This is a static country-level prototype, which will be extended to european and yearly coverage later"</i>. Annual maps of different functional trait (20m resolution) maps created using Sentinel-2 data and radiative transfer model inversion. We plan to present Geostories about the temporal change of functional traits (~ 5 different layers) for specific areas of interest. For instance, zoom in on a specific restoration/reforestation/disturbance event and show the time series of the development.</p>	Biodiversity	

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g19	SIF-based vegetation productivity proxy	World-carbon flux monitor	<p>We intend to present a Geostory about the capacity to evaluate vegetation response under heat stress based on satellite derived sun-induced chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF). This would be a proxy of GPP that is more sensitive to actual stress. We will start by data from a ready to use product from TROPOMI at 5 km resolution, but in later iterations we would provide a downscaled enhanced product. It would be good in the geostory to display the added increase in spatial resolution.</p> <p>We ultimately intend to make this last product using a DGGS grid (i.e. with hexagons on a sphere), which may require added visualization capacity.</p>	Climate & Health	
g20	Surface temperature change following afforestation	EU-land-based mitigation potential impact tool	<p>The geostory will illustrate the potential change in surface temperature that could be expected if low-level vegetation is changed to forest in different parts of Europe. We will begin with datasets based on MODIS to provide temperature at a specific time, and with a simple non-forest to forest transition. But in later versions we will move to MSG hourly data and we will ideally use more refined afforestation transitions. This means in latter versions of the story we will have to show a monthly mean daily cycle. It would also show different transitions, i.e. afforest with a deciduous species vs afforest with a needleleaf.</p>	Forest	
g21	Planet Health Index prototype	Planet Health Index	<p>The geostory will show how the planetary health index framework would work to allow users to explore the 3 main axes that respectively resume the "atmosphere", the "biosphere" and the "antroposphere". This is done at country level, showing how the indices for each sphere behave and evolve from 2000 to 2022. The idea is to showcase a couple of contrasting trajectories of some countries and point out how they are impacted by different events (e.g. COVID, financial crisis, etc). Please note that this will need to show graphs of time series, ideally in a 3D space, which may be an extra functionality that is not currently foreseen in the other geostories that are essentially map-based.</p>	Climate & Health	
g22	High resolution Snow Water Equivalent in selected alpine mountain regions	EU-snow monitor	<p>Snow Water Equivalent for Val Venosta. Decision makers need detailed information on the amount of water stored in the snowpack to improve how they manage water resources in a timely and efficient manner. The 50 m resolution Snow Water Equivalent maps and derivatives thereof allow optimizing the use of water resources in river management, hydro-energy production and agriculture. Browse through the daily timeseries to trace how the available water in the snowpack changes within a season and throughout the years.</p>	Water	Snow Water Equivalent (2017-2022)
g23	Climate change (Europe)	<p>EU-climate monitor</p> <p>Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset</p>	<p>Change in max., min., mean temperature, sea-level pressure, and total precipitation across Europe can be analysed at 2 levels:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Annual annual summaries maps are used to detect the changes between two periods 2) Changes from year to year can be analysed from annual summaries. 	Climate & Health	

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g24	Climate change (global)	Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset EU-climate monitor	Change in for max., min., mean temperature, sea-level pressure, and total precipitation at global scale can be analysed at 2 levels: 1) Annual long-term means (LTM) maps are used to detect the changes between two periods 2) Changes from year to year can be analysed from annual summaries.	Climate & Health	
g25	Trait-based reforestation monitoring	World-reforestation monitor EU-biodiversity monitor	<i>"Disclaimer: The displayed maps are not yet the final products. This is a static EU-wide prototype, which will be extended to global and yearly coverage later".</i> Annual maps of forest traits (~20m resolution) maps. The maps are derived from Sentinel-2 data by performing radiative transfer model inversion. We plan to display specific reforestation/disturbance events and show the time series evolution of the trait values for these plots.	Forest	
g26	Planet Health Index prequel	Planet Health Index	An interactive map of the world showing the countries. When the user selects one of the countries, the time series of the socioeconomic indices will be shown in a sub-plot. The user will be able to select two or more countries to compare the trajectories.	Climate & Health	
g27	Preliminary space for time on land cover change	EU-land-based mitigation potential impact tool	Mapping the potential biophysical effects of vegetation cover change	Forest	
g28	SIF-based proxy for GPP (coarse resolution)	World-carbon flux monitor	GPP is a measure of the capacity of ecosystems to capture carbon through the process of photosynthesis. Terrestrial ecosystems will display different patterns of GPP depending of the environmental and meteorological conditions to which that ecosystem is subjected to. SIF is a signal that can be retrieved from some remote sensing satellites and which can serve as a proxy of GPP. However, as past satellite instruments have never been designed to retrieve SIF, the resulting measurements are generally too coarse for many applications. The data shown here originally comes from the GOME2 instrument, which are gridded into cells/pixels of around 50 km. However, tools have been developed to increase the spatial resolution based on other satellite observations and some modelling assumptions. The resulting data shown here is thus at 5 km, allowing to illustrate patterns of growth across spatio-temporal gradients with much finer detail. The example illustrates how ecosystems, dominated by croplands, start capturing carbon in central France in the early spring ahead of surrounding areas, but by mid-June high growth rates have been reached across most of Western Europe.	Climate & Health	

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g29	Forest Time Machine	EU-forest management tool EU-rapid forest disturbance monitor	Travel through time and space to discover, through the eyes of historians and their historic cartographic documents and maps, and the lens of satellites, the changing landscape of forests in a Carpathian region, with an intricate past, the Bukovina region, within the Romanian territory. Defined by its forests - the Habsburgs called Buchenwald meaning Beech Land (from the slavic word "buk" = beech), the noun "bucovina" meaning beech forest - today it is a forestry region dominated by spruce! How did that happen? Data used: Austrian military maps (XVIII, XIX), Austrian/Romanian/Polish military topo maps (1900 - 1950), Corona Spy satellite imagery (1959 - 1972), Soviet military maps (1970 - 1985), National topo maps (1970 - present), Landsat and Sentinel 2.	Forest	
g30	Ocean net primary production (NPP)	EU-coastal monitor	The net primary productivity of the marine environment contributes between 45% and 50% to global productivity, playing a fundamental role in maintaining the global ecological balance and supporting life on Earth. In order to understand the distribution of biodiversity on our planet, it is essential to understand its variability over time and space.	Biodiversity	
g31	Air Quality during COVID-19 (Europe)	EU-air quality monitor	Air pollution is a health risk to millions of people in Europe. An indicator for air quality is the concentration of particles with a size of ~10 µm (PM10). Heavier pollution occurs in densely populated or industrial areas where we can observe more combustion of fossil fuels. The COVID-19 pandemic made many citizens remain at home when Europe went into lockdown. This sudden decline in demand for transport and industrial production had a positive impact on air quality in many regions. Check out the time series animation of monthly PM10 maps to get insights into air pollution in Europe throughout the years 2019 and 2020. Use the layer compare tool to inspect the differences between single time steps, for example April 2019 vs April 2020.	Climate & Health	Monthly PM10 Air Quality (2019-2020)